

Polarized Spatial Scattering Modulation

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Abstract—In this letter, a novel polarized spatial scattering modulation (PSSM), which exploits the available degree of freedom in the polarization domain in addition to the spatial scattering and signal domains to increase the spectral efficiency, is proposed. At the receiver, the maximum likelihood algorithm is applied to detect received signals. A tight union upper bound on the average bit error probability (ABEP) is derived in a closed-form. For the sake of fast system evaluation and comparison, an asymptotic bound on the ABEP is derived. Numerical results show that the proposed PSSM outperforms the conventional spatial scattering modulation and maximum beamforming systems in terms of the ABEP.

Index Terms—Spatial scattering modulation, polarized spatial scattering modulation, average bit error probability, asymptotic average bit error probability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, multiple input multiple output (MIMO) technologies have been employed to achieve a higher spectral efficiency for wireless communication systems [1]. The idea of the single radio frequency (RF) chain MIMO first appeared in the spatial modulation (SM) that uses only one RF chain at the transmitter has been widely investigated [2], [3].

In order to reduce the size of the antenna array in the single-RF MIMO system, a dual-polarized (DP)-SM has been proposed in [4]. In the DP-SM system, the information is conveyed simultaneously by quadrature signals, two orthogonal polarization states and antenna spaces. To further increase the spectral efficiency in the polarization domain, the polarization shift keying (PolarSK) was investigated [5], [6]. In the PolarSK system, information bits are conveyed by the selection of the polarization state of the transmit signal among linear polarizations, circular polarizations and elliptic polarizations.

Recently, spatial scattering modulation (SSM), as a novel single RF MIMO technology that uses the spatial scattering domain to convey information bits, was proposed by [7]. In the SSM, phase shifters are employed at the transmitter to form a directional beam. To further increase the spectral efficiency, an adaptive SSM system was proposed in [8]. However, only uni-polarized (UP) antennas have been used in existing SSM systems. To the best of our knowledge, the SSM system with polarized signal has not been investigated before.

Therefore, in this letter, a novel polarized SSM (PSSM) is proposed. In the PSSM, a polarized signal is generated

The research is funded in part by H2020-MSCA IF-AceLSAA (752644), in part by International Science and Technology Cooperation Program of China (2017YFE0118900), and in part by Natural Science Foundation of Gansu Province, China (18JR3RA268).

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Fig. 1. System model of the PSSM.

and transmitted by an array of dual-polarized (DP) antennas following the rule of the PolarSK. The polarized signal is steered to a scatterer following the rule of SSM. Two bit streams are transmitted simultaneously in the proposed PSSM. One of them is conveyed by the indices of polarization states whereas the other is conveyed by the directions of scattering clusters.

Moreover, a tight union upper bound (UUB) on the average bit error probability (ABEP) of the proposed PSSM is derived in a closed-form. The tightness of the UUB is validated through Monte-Carlo simulations. Moreover, an asymptotic bound on the ABEP is derived for the fast system evaluation and comparison. Numerical results show that the proposed PSSM has a better performance than the conventional SSM in terms of the ABEP.

II. TRANSMISSION SCHEME

The PSSM system with N_t DP antennas at the transmitter and N_r DP antennas at the receiver is shown in Fig. 1. We assume that there are N_{ts} scatterers in the wireless channel. In the transmission, we select N_s scatterers with the largest cluster gains for switching. In each transmission, $\lfloor \log_2 KM^2 \rfloor + \lfloor \log_2 N_s \rfloor$ bits are transmitted, where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor operation. The first $\lfloor \log_2 KM^2 \rfloor$ bits are mapped onto KM^2 different polarization states, and the other $\lfloor \log_2 N_s \rfloor$ bits are mapped onto N_s directions of different spatial scattering clusters. We assume that the transmitter knows channel state information (CSI). At the receiver, the maximum likelihood (ML) algorithm is used to detect received signals.

The channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{2N_r \times 2N_t}$ is modeled by

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{n_s=1}^{N_{ts}} \beta_{n_s} [\mathbf{h}_r(\theta_{n_s}^r) \mathbf{h}_t^H(\theta_{n_s}^t)] \otimes \mathbf{X}_{n_s}, \quad (1)$$

where \otimes denotes Kronecker product, $\beta_{n_s} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ denotes the complex gain of the n_s -th scatterer,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{h}_t(\theta_{n_s}^t) \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} [1, e^{j2\pi\psi_{n_s}^t}, \dots, e^{j2\pi\psi_{n_s}^t(N_t-1)}]^T, \\ \mathbf{h}_r(\theta_{n_s}^r) \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_r}} [1, e^{j2\pi\psi_{n_s}^r}, \dots, e^{j2\pi\psi_{n_s}^r(N_r-1)}]^T, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$\psi_{n_s}^t \triangleq \frac{d_t}{\lambda} \sin(\theta_{n_s}^t)$, $\psi_{n_s}^r \triangleq \frac{d_r}{\lambda} \sin(\theta_{n_s}^r)$, d_t and d_r denote the antenna spacing at the receiver and the transmitter, λ denotes the wavelength in the free space, $\theta_{n_s}^r$, $\theta_{n_s}^t$, denote the angle of arrival (AoA) and the angle of departure (AoD) of the n_s -th scatter, respectively [7].

$$\mathbf{X}_{n_s} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \exp(j\phi_{n_s,VV}) & \sqrt{X} \exp(j\phi_{n_s,HV}) \\ \sqrt{X} \exp(j\phi_{n_s,VH}) & \exp(j\phi_{n_s,HH}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

and X is the expectation of the power ratio between co-polarized and cross-polarized channels because of the imperfect cross-polar isolation (XPI) and the cross-polar ratio (XPR) [10], $\phi_{n_s,VV}$, $\phi_{n_s,HV}$, $\phi_{n_s,VH}$, $\phi_{n_s,HH}$ are all uniformly distributed variables from 0 to 2π .

With large N_t and N_r , the beams are narrow enough and the interference between scatters are negligible. Following [9], we assume that $\mathbf{h}_r^H(\theta_{n_s}^r) \mathbf{h}_r(\theta_{l_s}^r) \approx 0$, $n_s \neq l_s$, $\mathbf{h}_t^H(\theta_{n_s}^t) \mathbf{h}_t(\theta_{l_s}^t) \approx 0$, $n_s \neq l_s$.

Both the M -phase shift keying (PSK) constellations and the polarization states of signals are determined simultaneously by the amplitude and phase of signals. Thus, the following polarization constellations in this letter are employed [5]

$$\mathbf{s}_\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} s_{V,\zeta} \\ s_{H,\zeta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varepsilon_k \exp\left(\frac{j2\pi q_V}{M}\right) \\ \sin \varepsilon_k \exp\left(\frac{j2\pi q_H}{M}\right) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $\zeta = (k, q_V, q_H)$ specifies the index of the PolarSK signal, which will be transmitted by a DP transmit antenna. In particular, ε_k denotes the polarized angle of the Poincaré sphere, which has K circles of latitude. $q_V = 1, 2, \dots, M$ and $q_H = 1, 2, \dots, M$, respectively denote the indices of phases transmitted by vertically and horizontally polarized antennas.

At the transmitter, to steer the polarized signal to the direction of the n_s -th scatter, the weights of phase shifters $\mathbf{P}_{t,n_s} \in \mathbb{C}_{2N_t \times 2}$ are given as follows

$$\mathbf{P}_{t,n_s} = \mathbf{h}_t(\theta_{n_s}^t) \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

At the receiver, N_s sets of phase shifters are used to receive the signal from N_s scatters, respectively. The weights of the n_s -th set $\mathbf{P}_{r,n_s} \in \mathbb{C}_{2N_r \times 2}$ are given by

$$\mathbf{P}_{r,n_s} = \mathbf{h}_r(\theta_{n_s}^r) \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Output of each set of phase shifters, i.e., the received signal from its corresponding scatter, is fed into a pair of receive RF chains, and therefore $2N_s$ RF chains are employed at the receiver. Then, we obtain the received signal at the \tilde{n}_s -th pair of receive RF chains as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_{\tilde{n}_s} &= \sqrt{\rho} \beta_{\tilde{n}_s} \mathbf{P}_{r,\tilde{n}_s}^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_{t,n_s} \mathbf{s}_\zeta + \mathbf{w}_{\tilde{n}_s} \\ &= \begin{cases} \sqrt{\rho} \beta_{n_s} \mathbf{X}_{n_s} \mathbf{s}_\zeta + \mathbf{w}_{n_s}, & \tilde{n}_s = n_s, \\ \mathbf{w}_{\tilde{n}_s}, & \tilde{n}_s \neq n_s. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where ρ denotes the average signal to noise ratio, and $\mathbf{w}_{\tilde{n}_s} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_{2 \times 1}, \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2})$ denotes the additive white Gaussian noise of the \tilde{n}_s -th pair of receive RF chains.

Applying the ML algorithm, the detection of the received signal is given by

$$[\hat{\zeta}, \hat{n}_s] = \arg \min_{\zeta, \hat{n}_s} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left\| \mathbf{y}_{\hat{n}_s} - \sqrt{\rho} \beta_{\hat{n}_s} \mathbf{X}_{\hat{n}_s} \mathbf{s}_\zeta \right\|^2 \\ & + \sum_{\tilde{n}_s \neq \hat{n}_s=1}^{N_s} \left\| \mathbf{y}_{\tilde{n}_s} \right\|^2 \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (8)$$

III. OPTIMIZATION OF C_2 CONSTELLATION

In this section, we optimize the system constellation for C_2 that is the case with two circles of latitude ($K = 2$) in the PSSM. A too small $\Delta\varepsilon$ leads to the distance between constellation point k and \hat{k} too closest to be detected effectively. Otherwise, a large $\Delta\varepsilon$ leads to the distance between constellation point q and \hat{q} too closest to be detected effectively. Therefore, we maximize the minimum Euclidean distance to get the optimum $\Delta\varepsilon$.

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \operatorname{argmax}_{\Delta\varepsilon} \min_{s_\zeta, s_{\hat{\zeta}}} \left[\left\| \mathbf{s}_\zeta - \mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}} \right\|^2 \right]. \quad (9)$$

If $\hat{k} = k$, $\varepsilon_k = \varepsilon_{\hat{k}} = \frac{\pi}{4} + \Delta\varepsilon$, and with $|\Delta q_V| = 1$, $|\Delta q_H| = 0$, or $|\Delta q_V| = 0$, $|\Delta q_H| = 1$, the smallest Euclidean distance is obtained for $\hat{k} = k$. After some manipulations, we have

$$\min_{s_\zeta, s_{\hat{\zeta}}} \left\| \mathbf{s}_\zeta - \mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}} \right\|^2 = 2 \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \Delta\varepsilon \right)^2 \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi}{M} \right). \quad (10)$$

Else if $\hat{k} \neq k$, $\varepsilon_k = \frac{\pi}{4} + \Delta\varepsilon$, $\varepsilon_{\hat{k}} = \frac{\pi}{4} - \Delta\varepsilon$, and with $|\Delta q_V| = 0$, $|\Delta q_H| = 0$, the smallest Euclidean distance is obtained for $\hat{k} \neq k$. After some manipulations, we have

$$\min_{s_\zeta, s_{\hat{\zeta}}} \left\| \mathbf{s}_\zeta - \mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}} \right\|^2 = 4 \sin \Delta\varepsilon^2. \quad (11)$$

By maximizing the minimum Euclidean distance, we have

$$2 \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{4} + \Delta\varepsilon \right)^2 \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi}{M} \right) = 4 \sin \Delta\varepsilon^2. \quad (12)$$

The optimal $\Delta\varepsilon$ is the minimum positive real root of (12). After some manipulations, we obtain

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \left(\frac{\sin^4 \frac{\pi}{M} - \sin^2 \frac{\pi}{M} + \sqrt{2} \sin \frac{\pi}{M}}{\sin^4 \frac{\pi}{M} + 1} \right). \quad (13)$$

Then, the transmit signal expressed by (4) is generated with $\varepsilon_k = \frac{\pi}{4} \pm \Delta\varepsilon$.

IV. ABEP ANALYSIS

Using the UUB technology, the ABEP of the proposed PSSM system is upper bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} ABEP &\leq \sum_{n_s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{\hat{n}_s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{\zeta=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \sum_{\hat{\zeta}=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \\ &\quad \times \frac{[N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta}) + N(n_s, \hat{n}_s)] P(n_s, \zeta, \hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})}{N_s M^2 K \log_2(N_s M^2 K)}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $\zeta = (k, q_V, q_H)$, $\hat{\zeta} = (\hat{k}, \hat{q}_V, \hat{q}_H)$, $N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta})$ denotes the number of wrong bits by comparing ζ and $\hat{\zeta}$, and $N(n_s, \hat{n}_s)$ denotes the number of wrong bits by comparing n_s and \hat{n}_s . $P(n_s, \zeta, \hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})$ is the pairwise error probability (PEP) which is defined as the probability that the receiver selects the wrong symbol $[\hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta}]$ assuming that only two symbols (n_s, ζ) and $(\hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})$ are being transmitted. Note that (14) indicates that the closed-form expression for the UUB can be obtained as long as a closed-form expression for the PEP is available.

A. PEP for $\hat{n}_s = n_s$

For $\hat{n}_s = n_s$, as long as detection errors occurred at the receiver, ζ is wrongly detected as $\hat{\zeta}$. Then the PEP can be rewritten as

$$P(n_s, \zeta, n_s, \hat{\zeta}) = P_r[\|\mathbf{w}_{n_s}\|^2 > \|\mathbf{y}_{\hat{n}_s} - \sqrt{\rho}\beta_{n_s}\mathbf{X}_{n_s}\mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}}\|^2] \\ = \mathbb{E}_{\theta_{11}, \theta_{12}} \left[Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\rho[A+B(\cos\theta_{11}+\cos\theta_{12})]}{2}} \right) \right], \quad (15)$$

where $A \triangleq (1+X)|\beta_{n_s}|^2(|\Delta\mathbf{s}_V|^2 + |\Delta\mathbf{s}_H|^2)$, $B \triangleq 2\sqrt{X}|\beta_{n_s}|^2|\Delta\mathbf{s}_V\Delta\mathbf{s}_H|$, $[\theta_{11} \ \theta_{12}] \triangleq \angle(\mathbf{X}_{n_s}\Delta\mathbf{s})$, and $\Delta\mathbf{s} \triangleq \mathbf{s}_{\zeta} - \mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}} = [\Delta\mathbf{s}_V \ \Delta\mathbf{s}_H]$. Using $Q(x) \approx \frac{1}{12} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{4} \exp\left(\frac{-2x^2}{3}\right)$ and $I_s(x) \triangleq \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \exp(x \cos \theta) \cos(s\theta) d\theta$, we have

$$P(n_s, \zeta, n_s, \hat{\zeta}) = \frac{1}{12} \exp\left(-\frac{\rho A}{4}\right) I_0\left(\frac{\rho B}{4}\right) \\ + \frac{1}{4} \exp\left(-\frac{\rho A}{3}\right) I_0\left(\frac{\rho B}{3}\right). \quad (16)$$

B. PEP for $\hat{n}_s \neq n_s$

For $\hat{n}_s \neq n_s$, the PEP can be rewritten as

$$P(n_s, \zeta, n_s, \hat{\zeta}) = P_r[\|\mathbf{w}_{n_s}\|^2 > \|\mathbf{y}_{\hat{n}_s} - \sqrt{\rho}\beta_{\hat{n}_s}\mathbf{X}_{\hat{n}_s}\mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}}\|^2] \\ = \mathbb{E}_\lambda \{P_r[\chi_1 > \chi_2(\lambda)]\}, \quad (17)$$

where χ_1 is a chi-squared distributed random variable with four degrees of freedom, and χ_2 is a non-central distributed random variable with four degrees of freedom. The non-centrality parameter is defined by

$$\lambda = 2\rho|\beta_{\hat{n}_s}|^2\|\mathbf{X}_{\hat{n}_s}\mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}}\|^2 \\ = 2\rho|\beta_{\hat{n}_s}|^2[1+X+2\sqrt{X}|s_{V,\hat{\zeta}}s_{H,\hat{\zeta}}|(\cos\theta_{21}+\cos\theta_{22})], \quad (18)$$

where $[\theta_{21} \ \theta_{22}] = \angle(\mathbf{X}_{\hat{n}_s}\mathbf{s}_{\hat{\zeta}})$. Using the probability density function (PDF) of the chi-squared and non-central chi-squared random variables, we have

$$\Pr[\chi_1 > \chi_2(\lambda)] = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{x_2}^{+\infty} f_{\chi_1}(x_1)f_{\chi_2}(x_2)dx_1dx_2. \quad (19)$$

After some manipulations, we have

$$\Pr[\chi_1 > \chi_2(\lambda)] = \frac{\exp(-\frac{\lambda}{2})}{8} \int_0^{+\infty} x_2(x_2+2) \\ \times \exp(-x_2) {}_0F_1\left(; 2, \frac{\lambda x_2}{4}\right) dx_2. \quad (20)$$

Since ${}_0F_1\left(; 2, z\right) = \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{z^n}{n!(n+1)!}$, we obtain

$$\Pr[\chi_1 > \chi_2(\lambda)] = \frac{\exp(-\frac{\lambda}{2})}{8} \int_0^{+\infty} x_2(x_2+2) \exp(-x_2) \\ \times \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{n!(n+1)!} \left(\frac{\lambda x_2}{4}\right)^n dx_2. \quad (21)$$

Exchanging the order of the integral and the summation, and using $\int_0^{+\infty} x_2^n \exp(-x_2) dx_2 = n!$, we have

$$\Pr[\chi_1 > \chi_2(\lambda)] = \frac{\exp(-\frac{\lambda}{2})}{8} \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{n+4}{n!} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4}\right)^n \\ = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4} + 4\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda}{4}\right). \quad (22)$$

Substituting (18) and (22) into (17), we obtain

$$P(n_s, \zeta, \hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta}) = \frac{4+\rho C}{8} \exp(-\rho C) [I_0(\rho D)]^2 \\ - \frac{\rho D}{4} \exp(-\rho C) I_0(\rho D) I_1(\rho D), \quad (23)$$

where $C \triangleq |\beta_{\hat{n}_s}|^2 \frac{(1+X)}{2}$, and $D \triangleq |\beta_{\hat{n}_s}|^2 \sqrt{X} |s_{V,\hat{\zeta}} s_{H,\hat{\zeta}}|$. It is observed that $P(n_s, \zeta, \hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})$ is irrelevant to n_s and ζ .

C. Simplification of the UUB

By reforming (14), we obtain

$$ABEP \leq \sum_{n_s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{\zeta=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \sum_{\hat{\zeta}=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \frac{N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta}) P(n_s, \zeta, n_s, \hat{\zeta})}{N_s M^2 K \log_2(N_s M^2 K)} + \\ \sum_{n_s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{\hat{n}_s \neq n_s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{\zeta=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \sum_{\hat{\zeta}=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \frac{[N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta}) + N(n_s, \hat{n}_s)] P(n_s, \zeta, \hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})}{N_s M^2 K \log_2 N_s M^2 K}. \quad (24)$$

When $\hat{n}_s \neq n_s$, $P(\hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})$ is irrelevant to n_s and ζ . Furthermore, when $\hat{n}_s \neq n_s$, \hat{n}_s and $\hat{\zeta}$ are randomly chosen, i.e., $N(n_s, \hat{n}_s) = \frac{N_s \log_2 N_s}{2(N_s-1)}$ and $N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta}) = 0.5 \log_2(M^2 K)$ [11]. Therefore, we can simplify the ABEP expression as

$$ABEP \leq \sum_{n_s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{\zeta=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \sum_{\hat{\zeta}=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \frac{N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta}) P(n_s, \zeta, n_s, \hat{\zeta})}{N_s M^2 K \log_2(N_s M^2 K)} \\ + \sum_{\hat{n}_s=1}^{N_s} \frac{M^2 K [(N_s-1) \log_2(M^2 K) + N_s \log_2 N_s] P(n_s, \zeta, \hat{n}_s, \hat{\zeta})}{2N_s \log_2(N_s M^2 K)}. \quad (25)$$

D. Asymptotic ABEP

In this subsection, we derive an asymptotic ABEP in the high signal noise ratio (SNR) region. Before the derivations in below, we define the notation “ \doteq ”. Assuming that $f_1(\rho)$ and $f_2(\rho)$ are two functions of ρ , and as long as $\lim_{\rho \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{f_1(\rho)}{f_2(\rho)} = 1$, we denote that $f_1(\rho) \doteq f_2(\rho)$. By using this definition, we have $I_n(x\rho) \doteq \frac{\exp(x\rho)}{\sqrt{2\pi x\rho}}$.

For $\alpha_m, \beta_m, \gamma_n$, and $\eta_n \in \mathbb{R}^+$, (26), provided at the bottom of this page, holds. Thus, substituting (16) and (23) into (25), we obtain an expression for the asymptotic ABEP as

$$ABEP_{\text{asy}} \doteq \begin{cases} \gamma \exp(-\rho\eta), & \beta \geq \eta, \\ \alpha \rho^{-1} \exp(-\rho\beta), & \beta < \eta, \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \beta \triangleq \min_{n_s, \zeta, \hat{\zeta}} \left(\frac{A-2B}{4}\right), \eta \triangleq \min_{\hat{n}_s} (C-2D), \\ \alpha \triangleq \sum_{\zeta=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \sum_{\hat{\zeta}=(1,1,1)}^{M,M,K} \frac{\delta\left(\frac{A-2B}{4}-\beta\right) N(\zeta, \hat{\zeta})}{6\pi B M^2 K \log_2(N_s M^2 K)}, \\ \gamma \triangleq \sum_{\hat{n}_s=1}^{N_s} \frac{M^2 K \delta(C-2D-\eta) \left[\frac{(N_s-1) \log_2(M^2 K)}{+N_s \log_2 N_s}\right] (C-2D)}{32\pi D N_s \log_2(N_s M^2 K)}, \\ \delta(x) \triangleq \begin{cases} 1, & x = 0, \\ 0, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} \sum_m \alpha_m \rho^{-1} \exp(-\rho\beta_m) \\ + \sum_n \gamma_n \exp(-\rho\eta_n) \end{array} \right] \doteq \begin{cases} \exp(-\rho \min\{\eta_n\}) \sum_n \gamma_n \delta(\eta_n - \min\{\eta_n\}), & \min\{\beta_m\} \geq \min\{\eta_m\}, \\ \exp(-\rho \min\{\beta_m\}) \sum_m \alpha_m \rho^{-1} \delta(\beta_m - \min\{\beta_m\}), & \min\{\beta_m\} < \min\{\eta_m\}. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Fig. 2. ABEP performance of the proposed C_1 -based PSSM system.

Fig. 3. ABEP performance of the proposed C_2 -based PSSM system.

V. NUMERIAL RESULTS

In our simulations, considering a non-line-of-sight (NLOS) scenario, we choose $N_t = N_r = 16$ DP antennas in the PSSM system whereas $N_t = N_r = 32$ UP antennas in the SSM and maximum beamforming (MBF) systems. The transmitter of the MBF selects the largest gain β_{n_1} scatter to convey information. M -PSK and quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) are respectively employed with the SSM and MBF. We assume that $N_{ts}=10$ and $X=7$ dB. In the PSSM system, C_1 and C_2 constellations are employed.

In Figs. 2 and 3, we verify the tightness of the analytic closed-form ABEP via Monte Carlo simulations for 1×10^5 realizations. For $M=4$ and $N_s=(2,4)$, C_1 and C_2 constellations are considered. For C_1 and C_2 constellations, it is observed that the PSSM with $N_s=2$ and $M=4$ has a better ABEP performance than that of the PSSM with $N_s=4$ and $M=4$. In addition, the asymptotic ABEP matches the upper bound on the analytic closed-form ABEP in the high SNR region.

We denote the d_{PSSM} , d_{SSM} and d_{MBF} the minimum Euclidean distances of PSSM, SSM and MBF, respectively. At the data rate of 5 bpcu, following the M -PSK/QAM, we have $d_{PSSM} = 1$, $d_{SSM} = 2 \sin(\frac{\pi}{16})$ and $d_{MBF} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{26}}$, and thus $d_{PSSM} > d_{MBF} > d_{SSM}$. Since the minimum Euclidean distance determines the ABEP [12, Lemma 1], we can predict that the ABEP of the proposed PSSM at the data rate of 5 bpcu is lower than that of the MBF and SSM. From Fig. 4, we observe that PSSM, SSM, and MBF respectively require 20, 23.5, and 24.5 dB SNR to achieve a 10^{-6} ABEP. Similar observations are obtained for systems at data rates of 6 and 7 bpcu. Therefore, the proposed PSSM system have a lower ABEP than the conventional SSM and MBF systems.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this letter, a novel PSSM system has been proposed to enhance the spectral efficiency of the SSM system by exploiting the degree of freedom available in the polarization domain. An UUB and an asymptotic bound on the ABEP have been both derived in closed-forms. At a same spectral efficiency, the minimum Euclidean distance between the closest pair of points in the PSSM system is greater than that of the conventional SSM and MBF systems. Therefore, we can conclude that the proposed PSSM system outperforms the conventional SSM and MBF systems in terms of the ABEP.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the PSSM with SSM and MBF. In the PSSM system, the C_1 constellation is employed. At the data of 5 bpcu, we choose PSSM with $M=4$, $N_s=2$, SSM with $M=16$, $N_s=2$, and MBF with $M=32$, $N_s=2$. At the data of 6 bpcu, we choose PSSM with $M=4$, $N_s=4$, SSM with $M=16$, $N_s=4$, and MBF with $M=64$, $N_s=1$.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the PSSM with SSM and MBF. In the PSSM system, the C_2 constellation is employed. At the data of 6 bpcu, we choose PSSM with $M=4$, $N_s=2$, SSM with $M=32$, $N_s=2$, and MBF with $M=32$, $N_s=1$. At the data of 7 bpcu, we choose PSSM with $M=4$, $N_s=4$, SSM with $M=32$, $N_s=4$, and MBF with $M=128$, $N_s=1$.

In our future research works, we will combine the proposed PSSM system, generalized space shift keying, and beam steering to trade off between the spectral efficiency and reliability.

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